

101034439 - *Resolution*

Medical Genetic Solutions for RESOLUTE

WP3 – Resource of variant-specific data on SLC genes with medical annotation

D3.2 Data Modelling and ETL Pipelines documentation

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Abstract

As extensively outlined in the Data Management Plan (DMP, Deliverable 3.1), REsolution will share the data infrastructure developed over the past years by RESOLUTE. One of the main tasks the Work Package 3 (WP3) is to extend the data models present in this data repository to accommodate the variant-specific Solute Carriers (SLC) data mined by the WP1, the novel experimental information produced by the WP2 and the integrative analyses provided by the WP4. Data management Work Packages from both the consortia will work alongside to ensure the harmonization of the models across both projects.

Additionally, REsolution proposes a framework for the extract-transform-load (ETL) processes. This framework revolves around the use of Nextflow, Docker and the Azure Cloud. These resources are established in modern computational research's best practice and will help the consortium to achieve the highest standards of research quality.

Data Model

The relational structure of RESOLUTE's Knowledge/Database will be expanded by introducing data models tailored to the new information brought by REsolution.

Genetic variants model

The core of the data produced within REsolution revolves around genetic variants. Genetic information in the proposed model is described with the following set of hierarchical entities: genes, transcripts, variants, transcript-specific variants, and protein variants.

- The *Gene* table provides information for the SLC's gene. Attributes include the name of the SLC, the chromosome and the coding strand. The ENSEMBL stable identifier is used to unequivocally identify each gene.
- The *Transcript* table is needed as SLCs can have multiple isoforms. Transcript coordinates, length in base-pairs, and the ENSEMBL transcript stable ID (identifier) can be retrieved from the table. Canonical transcripts are labeled and easily identified within the database.
- The *Variant* table provides all the main information used to describe a mutation on a DNA level, such as the genetic coordinates, the reference and the mutated alleles, and the reference genome. The ID for each variant is obtained from the combination of its chromosome, position, reference allele and mutated allele, separated by a "-" (e.g. 9-4490691-G-C). When available, the dbSNP Reference SNP (single-nucleotide polymorphism) ID will also be included.
- The *Transcript-Variant* table includes the attributes needed to characterize the impact of the variant on the individual transcript, such as the specific HGVS_c (Human Genome Variation Society coding sequence name) annotation and the coordinates of the alteration within the isoform.
- The *Protein-variant* table is available for variants affecting coding regions (e.g., missense, indels or synonymous variants). Coordinates on the polypeptide sequence, the reference and mutated amino acids, and the HGVS_p (Human Genome Variation Society protein sequence name) annotation are collected in this table.

Figure 1: Hierarchical structure of the variant data model.

Gene-level and Variant-level model

One of the goals of REsolution is to offer a centralized and curated collection of publicly available associations between SLC-specific genetic anomalies and phenotypic traits. The data model revolved around the separation of SLC-trait associations on a gene-level and on a variant-level.

Associations are described on a *gene-level* when changes in the normal functionality of the carrier can be observed but they are not linked to any specific genetic alteration. Conversely, if the change in the function is identified through specific mutations, associations are described on a *variant-level*.

A table will describe the association, by linking a specific trait either to a gene or variant. Moreover, it will provide information regarding the source of the information (e.g. a specific publicly accessible database). This simple model can unify information collected from the most diverse sources and potentially highlight potential consensus or differences among the public knowledge.

Figure 2: Hierarchical structure of the Gene-level and Variant-level data

Pipelines

ETL computational pipelines in REsolution will rely on 3 computational resources: Nextflow, Docker and Azure Cloud.

Nextflow

The main goal of the workflow managers is to provide the tools to finely structure the input-output data relationship between all the individual processes included in a pipeline. Their use in the research environment is consolidated not only because their implementation eases the development and the deployment of computational pipelines, but also because it ensures portability, scalability, and reproducibility of analyses. Nextflow, together with Snakemake, is one of the most common workflow managers in computational biology.

Nextflow natively supports the container technology (specifically, Docker and Singularity) and the cloud infrastructure (such as AWS, Google Cloud and Azure Cloud) REsolution relies on to ensure the FAIRness of data. Nextflow allows the users to customize the execution of all the containerized tools used by the pipeline, the management of the storage volumes, and monitor the execution of the analysis. Deployment of the pipeline is streamlined by the support to cloud platforms and other cluster managers. Nextflow provides the tools to properly submit the tasks to the Azure Cloud's processes scheduler, specify a set of computational resources tailored to each individual task, or the exact position of data within the cloud's storage space.

Pipelines developed using Nextflow will be shared via a REsolution GitHub private account.

Docker

As the landscape of third-party software needed by computational scientists is constantly evolving, ensuring a perfect reproducibility of results became a priority for pipeline development. Containers, also known as container images, are self-isolated computational environments that incorporate all the resources (such as scripts, libraries, configuration files, and so on) needed for the execution of a software. Contrary to proper virtual machines, containers run on top of the local machine's kernel, removing the need for computational heavy emulators, and making the images easily portable across different machines.

In REsolution, Nextflow oversees the managing of Docker containers. Whenever possible, analyses will rely on the official image files released by the official software authors via Docker Hub, that will serve as the main repository for Docker images used or developed throughout the project. Azure will provide both the computational resources needed to execute the analysis and the storage volumes for the input and output data. The combination of Docker's containerized nature and a careful customization of the cloud's batch scheduler will allow parallelizable, high-throughput and independently instanced analyses, even in case of executions of several processes that rely on the same container image.

Azure Cloud

With the advent of the big-data era in biomedical research, the use of HPC (High-Performance Computing) became essential. Most of the high-throughput computational analyses, once done on local machines, are now submitted to clusters of potent machines, able to process high computational-power demanding tasks. Cloud computing represents the further evolution of this process as all the resources are allocated on remote, easily accessible servers. Cloud providers relieve the users of the burden of the maintenance of the servers, while also providing the interfaces needed to tailor the service to the analysis's needs.

REsolution uses the Azure Cloud to easily exchange data between the consortium members and to provide a powerful and shared computational platform. Azure's tasks scheduler, Azure Batch, receives from Nextflow the list of steps the pipeline is made of and the directives for the vertical and horizontal scaling. The first involves the quantification of needed computational power (such as CPU and RAM) for each process, the second the number of virtual machines, clustered in the so-called Pools, required to parallelize several processes or multiple tasks within the same process. When Docker is required to perform a task, each Pool can independently access a container image and use it to run analysis. Moreover, Azure provides the volumes to store data involved in the analysis. The exact coordinates are provided by Nextflow and loaded in the container. Access to the cloud resources and volumes is restricted to the REsolution consortium partners.

The interaction between these three elements can ensure the FAIRfication of the data involved in the analysis (for more details about the FAIR principles please refer to the DMP).

- **Findability** : While not directly affecting the identifier convention, this pipeline development strategy will offer a documented record of all the input and output data involved in the analyses and their position coordinates within the Azure storage
- **Accessibility** : The Azure platform serves as a centralized storage space shared across all the consortium members. All the information, including the datasets non directly accessible through the

Web Portal, are easily reachable within this platform. Moreover, Nextflow's ability to communicate with the cloud makes it possible to perform all the computational analyses from any machine.

- **Interoperability** : Like Findability, Interoperability is not directly affected by the pipelines. However, the shared space and the direct, well-documented access to analyses will enhance communication between all the involved researchers and improve the review process as well.
- **Re-usability** : The fully automated, fine-structured and well-documented workflows produced by the Nextflow pipelines represent the core of modern computational research's best practice. Docker will play a protagonist role by enabling the perfect reproducibility of every step of the analysis.

Figure 3: A brief schema of the role of Nextflow, Azure and Docker and their interaction.

Appendix

Abbreviations

DMP	Data Management Plan
ETL	Extract, Transform, Load process used to copy data from one or several sources and insert to a destination system (e.g. database or data warehouse), which uses different data representation.
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
HPC	High-Performance Computing
ID	Identifier
IMI	Innovative Medicine Initiative
RESOLUTE	Research Empowerment on Solute Carriers
SLC	Solute Carrier
SNP	Single-nucleotide polymorphism
WP	Work Package

Consortium Members

short name	full name
CeMM	CeMM Research Center for Molecular Medicine of the Austrian Academy of Sciences
UoX	University of Oxford
UoL	University of Liverpool
AXXAM	Axxam SpA
ULei	Universiteit Leiden
MPIMR	Max-Planck Institut für medizinische Forschung
UniVie	Universität Wien
Pfizer	Pfizer Ltd.
Bayer	Bayer AG